

Heterocyclic Systems Containing Bridge Head Nitrogen Atom: Part I. Synthesis of 5H, 6H-Imidazo-[2,1-b]-Thiazolidin-3-one Hydrochloride

H. S. Chaudhari and H. K. Pujari

One step-convenient synthesis of 5H, 6H-imidazo-[2,1-b]-thiazolidin-3-one hydrochloride (III) has been achieved by condensing 2-mercapto-imidazoline (I) with ethylchloroacetate. Ten 2-arylidine-5H, 6H-imidazo-[2,1-b]-thiazolidin-3-ones have also been prepared. Some of the arylidene thiazolidones have been brominated.

In furtherance of 'our studies' on potential biologically active thiazolidones, we reported the synthesis of heterocyclic system² in which the thiazolidone ring was fused to benzimidazole ring. In the present work the synthesis of another heterocyclic system in which the thiazolidone ring is fused to imidazole ring is reported. This investigation was undertaken for the reason that the fusion of the thiazolidone ring with imidazole ring was expected to yield a compound more potent than the individual ones.

Campaigne and Wani³ synthesised compound III by two methods. In the first method, compound I, when reacted with sodium chloroacetate gave II, which on treatment with conc. HCl yielded III. In the second method, compound I was treated with ethyl chloroacetate in presence of sodium acetate in ethanol giving IV which on reacting with conc. HCl gave III.

1. H. K. Pujari, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 657.
2. H. S. Chaudhary and H. K. Pujari, Communicated, *Indian J. Chem.*
3. E. Campaigne and M. C. Wani, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 1715.

We, wish to report in the present investigations the one step-convenient synthesis of III. Compound I, when heated with excess of ethyl chloroacetate at 150° for 4 hrs. gave III. The identity of this compound was confirmed through its picrate.

It is well known that ethyl chloroacetate forms thiazolidones from various thioureas by forming a carbon-sulphur bond. Since the thiourea, used here, is a symmetrical cyclic thiourea, there is no ambiguity as to the direction of cyclisation. In compound III, the nitrogen atom not common to two rings is assumed to be more basic since it is not adjacent to a carbonyl group. As a result of its more basicity, it should quarternize more readily than the bridge head nitrogen atom.

Compound III, when condensed with benzaldehyde in presence of fused sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid gave benzylidene derivative (V, R=C₆H₅). van Allan⁴ also prepared compound (V, R=C₆H₅) by reacting compound I with ethyl chloroacetate and benzaldehyde in presence of piperidine in ethanol.

Other 2-arylidene-5H, 6H- imidazo-[2, 1-b]-thiazolidin-3-ones were, however, synthesised by the method of van Allan⁴ directly from compound I as it is one-step reaction.

Bromination of thiazolidone (III) and arylidene thiazolidone (V) was undertaken for two reasons, first, to obtain powerful fungicides and second, to test the validity of the assumption made by Farooq and Hunter⁵ that the keto-enol system present in the

4. J. A. van Allan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 24.

5. M.O. Farooq and R. F. Hunter, *This Journal*, 1932, **9**, 545.

tetrahydrothiazole derivatives does not take part in the production of the bromine addition compounds. This assumption was found to be correct in the present case and bromine did not enter the keto-enol system present in III. Arylidene thiazolidones (V), however, on bromination gave brominated thiazolidones (VI) and as expected bromine entered the ethylene linkage, proof of which is given as follows. When compound III, after reaction with bromine, was treated with sulphurous acid, the original compound (III) was recovered, thus excluding the possibility of (a) addition of bromine to the C=N double bond and (b) to the nuclear sulphur atom. When the compound (VI, R=HOC₆H₄-) was, however, refluxed with potassium hydroxide, potassium bromide precipitated, suggesting that bromine was attached to the aliphatic fragment of the molecule.

The evaluation of bactericidal and fungicidal properties of these compounds is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected.

2-mercapto-imidazoline (I) was prepared from ethylene diamine and carbon disulphide according to the method described by Allan et al.⁶

5H, 6H- *Imidazo*-[2-1-b]-*thiazolidin-3-one hydrochloride* (III): 2-mercapto-imidazoline (I) (5.1 g, 0.05 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (30 g) were heated on an oil-bath at 150° for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature when the whole of the content solidified to a dark brown solid. The crude product was decolourised by charcoal treatment in ethanol and the filtrate was then concentrated and kept in refrigerator overnight, when light yellow crystals separated. It was finally recrystallised from alcohol, yield 45%, m.p. 204-6° decomp. (Lit.³ m.p. 205-6° decomp.). (Found: S, 17.44, Cl, 19.39; C₅H₇ON₂SCl requires; S, 17.93, Cl, 19.89%). Picrate, m.p. 185° decomp. (Lit.³ m.p. 184-5° decomp.).

2-*Benzal-5H, 6H-imidazo*-[2,1-b]-*thiazolidin-3-one* (V, R=C₆H₅): (a) 5H, 6H-*Imidazo*-[2,1-b]-*thiazolidin-3-one hydrochloride* (III) (1.78 g, 0.01 mol), benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 0.01 mol), fused sodium acetate (2 g) and glacial acetic acid (15-20 ml) were heated under reflux on an asbestos centered wire gauge. The reaction mixture became clear within a few minutes of heating. After reflux for 4 hrs. it was cooled to room temperature and then poured into cold water when solid separated. The crude product

was filtered and crystallised from xylene giving pale yellow crystals, m.p. 182.3°, yield 45% (Found: S, 13.64, $C_{12}H_{10}ON_2S$, requires S, 13.91%).

(b) Compound (V, $R=C_6H_5$) was also prepared directly by refluxing compound I, ethyl chloroacetate, and benzaldehyde. The procedure adopted was that of van Allan⁴, m.p. 181.2°. (Lit.⁴ m.p. 180°).

The properties and analytical data of the other 2-arylidine-5H, 6H-Imidazo-[2, 1-b]-thiazolidin-3-ones prepared by method (b) are recorded in table I.

TABLE I
vide Structure V

No.	R	% Yield	Colour	m.p. °C	%Sulphur	
					Found	Calc.
7.	(<i>p</i>) Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	38	cream	228	11.96	12.10
8.	(<i>o</i>) HO-C ₆ H ₄ -	25	light yellow	235.6	13.04	13.01
9.	(<i>p</i>) HO-C ₆ H ₄ -	30	yellow	158	12.89	13.01
10.	(<i>m</i>) O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ -	35	dull yellow	233	11.54	11.64
11.	(<i>p</i>) MeO-C ₆ H ₄ -	20	pale yellow	185	11.88	12.30
12.	(3,4 MeO, (OH)C ₆ H ₃ -	40	cream	247	11.26	11.60
13.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	40	yellow	242	12.14	12.50
14.		35	dirty brown	173-5	14.32	14.47
15.		31	deep yellow	275 decomp.	10.63	11.15

Bromination of compound (V, R=(p)-HO-C₆H₄): Formation of VI, R=(p)-HO-C₆H₅: Compound V (1 g) in chloroform (30 ml) was treated with bromine (2 ml) in chloroform (5 ml) at 0-5° for about 2 hrs. On removal of the solvent under reduced pressure at room temperature a vermillion coloured bromine addition compound was obtained. On treatment with sulphurous acid and subsequent basification with ammonia it gave deep yellow dibromo derivative (VI) of V, m.p. 200°, yield 75% (Found: Br, 39.28, $C_{12}H_{10}N_2SO_2Br_2$ requires Br, 39.41%).

Table II describes the properties and analytical data of other bromine derivatives.

TABLE II
vide Structure VI

No.	R	Yield %	Colour	m.p. °C	%Bromine	
					Found	Calc.
16.	(<i>p</i>) Me O-C ₆ H ₄ -	85	pale yellow	211	37.85	38.09
17.	(3,4) Me O, (OH)C ₆ H ₃ -	50	yellow	252	36.34	36.69

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